

THE TRANSLATING OF ENGLISH EXTRAPOSITION CONSTRUCTIONS INTO AZERI

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Abstract

The aim of the research is to run the gamut of English extraposition constructions involving copular verbs, followed by “that-clause” and infinitive. Providing some evidence of the use of these constructions and comparing their translation in Azeri and investigating of linguistic properties are the purposes of this study. To this aim, the English fictions and their Azeri translations considered as sources of the data. The researcher classifies the data into two main categories: the extraposition constructions followed by “that”-clause and the extraposition constructions followed by “infinitive”. Based on 200 data, it has been cleared that in Azeri, the dummy subject “it” is not translated at all. Moreover, instead of copular verbs in Azeri translation, there are some expressions called “modal words”, functioning like verb phrases, are used according to the meaning of copular verbs. The total number of these sentences using modal words is 185 sentences. Regarding extraposition constructions followed by that-clause, it can be said that most of them translated as complex sentences in Azeri, with the percentage of 70%. However, extraposition constructions which involve infinitive, are translated as simple sentences with the percentage of 65%. This study uses a qualitative descriptive method.

Keywords: translation, extraposition constructions, copular verbs, “that-clause”, infinitive.

Rezumat

În articol, ne propunem să cercetăm construcțiile extrapozitionate în engleză și traducerea lor în azeră, adică construcțiile care înglobează verbe copulative, urmate de subordonata „that-clause” sau un verb la infinitiv. Drept exemplificare a postulatelor teoretice au servit texte literare în limba engleză și traducerea lor în limba azeră. Autoarea identifică două tipuri de construcție extrapozitionată: construcția cu subordonata „that-clause” și construcția cu verbul la infinitiv. În baza celor 200 de exemple analizate, autoarea demonstrează că în azeră, subiectul impersonal „it” nu are echivalent de traducere, iar în locul verbelor copulative, sunt întrebuințate, de cele mai dese ori, „cuvinte modale” care au funcția unor verbe copulative. Cu referire la construcțiile englezești extrapozitionate cu subordonata „that-clause”, se poate spune că 70% dintre ele se tradus, în azeră, prin propoziții compuse, iar 65% dintre construcțiile englezești extrapozitionate cu verbul la infinitiv sunt traduse, în azeră, prin propoziții simple. La baza acestui studiu a fost pusă metoda calitativ-descriptivă.

Cuvinte-cheie: traducere, construcții extrapozitionate, verbe copulative, „that-clause”, verb la infinitiv.

1. Introduction

Nowadays there is a tremendous interest in translation, since it is a channel through which ideas and cultures pass. In more recent time, translation comes to play a significance role in the politics, public and private organizations and many other aspects. It can be said that translation

is a profession besides being art. According to B. Hatim and J. Munday⁴⁷⁸ translation is a phenomenon that has a huge effect on everybody's life. P. Newmark defines translation as the attempt to produce approximate equivalence or respectable synonymy between two chunks of different languages on various levels of which two main ones are thought and linguistic form. This researcher adds that translation is partly an exercise in the art of writing as well as a field of comparative applied linguistics⁴⁷⁹. He believes that grammatical meaning is more significant, less precise, more general and sometimes more elusive than lexical meaning⁴⁸⁰. Basically, it will have attained this fact that syntactic differences existing among languages, may cause problem in translation. The translating of English extraposition constructions involving copular verbs, followed by that-clauses and infinitive, into Azeri is the aim of this paper. Since the syntactic pattern of Azeri and English is completely different in this respect, the translation of these constructions may cause some problems for Azerbaijanian translators, translator trainees and English learners. So having complete knowledge about structure of these sentences may be useful for them.

A. Miremadi believes that all languages show signs of noun phrases, events, prepositional phrases and etc., but they show differences in their formal distributions⁴⁸¹. E.A. Nida⁴⁸² argues that "in no two languages one can find exactly identical systems of structural organization based on which symbols can be related to meaning on the one-to-one correspondence basis". According to E.A. Nida word classes, grammatical relations, word order, style and pragmatic features are different from language to language⁴⁸³. A feature which may cause problems in translation is English extraposition constructions. According to B. Chocholoušova, among the constructions involving dummy subject, extraposition constructions are the most frequent type in materials in languages like English, Norwegian and German⁴⁸⁴. Therefore it seems necessary to have complete knowledge about this construction and its translation in Azeri. To this end English fictions are studied to identify these structures in English and their Azeri equivalents. In this relation, the following research questions have been formulated:

- (1) How are English extraposition constructions translated into Azeri?
- (2) Is English dummy subject "it" kept/replaced or omitted in Azeri translation?

⁴⁷⁸Hatim *et alii*, 2004, p. 38.

⁴⁷⁹Newmark, 1988, p. 26.

⁴⁸⁰*ibidem*.

⁴⁸¹Miremadi, 1991, p. 67.

⁴⁸²Nida, 1975, p. 24.

⁴⁸³*ibidem*.

⁴⁸⁴Chocholoušova, 2007, p. 49.

2. Translation and Translation Problems

According to E.A. Nida⁴⁸⁵, “translation is the reproduction in a closest natural equivalent of the source language message”. It means that a translation should tell the content and some meaning of the original text⁴⁸⁶.

Translation itself means a process of replacing/reproducing /transferring from the source language of written text/material concept into its target language⁴⁸⁷. W. Wilss believes that translation is a transfer process which aims at the transformation of a written source language into an optimally equivalent target language and which requires the syntactic, semantic and pragmatic understanding and analytical processing of the source language. Generally, it can be said that in the present era of globalization, translation plays a major role in conveying messages from one language to another. However translation is not an easy task. Since languages express grammatical and lexical relationships in different ways, therefore, in rendering texts, the translators are always surrounded by a number of problems which are to be tackled consciously and accurately. A. Miremadi believes that the first problem is how to get access to adequate comprehending of the original text with all its complexities⁴⁸⁸. According to Kopezynski⁴⁸⁹, the translator should possess a transcoding mechanism to enable him:

(a) to make accurate interpretation of the totality of the source and target language;

(b) to carry out an adequate conversion of the source language grammar into the target language grammar;

(c) to make generalization based on intertraffic between the two languages to seek equivalents.

The second problem is the existence of lexical, syntactic, semantic, pragmatic and the word perspective imbalance between languages. Because of differences between languages, there is no completely exact translation between any two languages. According to Werner⁴⁹⁰, “the degree of similarity between the systems of any two languages determines the efficacy of the translation made”.

The other problem in translation is lexical problem. Words are entities which refer to object or concepts.

There is no an identical object in the two cultures. Thus in translating texts, all differences have to be taken into account and must be considered as

⁴⁸⁵Nida, 1975.

⁴⁸⁶*idem*, p. 41.

⁴⁸⁷Karnadidjaya, 2001, p. 4.

⁴⁸⁸Miremadi, 1992, p. 98.

⁴⁸⁹Kopezynski, *apud* Miremadi, 1992.

⁴⁹⁰Werner, *apud* Golestani, 2006.

an important factor. In this case the denotative meaning, connotative meaning and ironical meanings are so important and translator's misunderstanding of any of these words and elements may end in a translation reality and moral sense.

Another factor which may cause problem in translations is syntactic problem. It can be said that syntax is the study of the rules to form or to make grammatical sentences in a language or the study of pattern of sentences and phrase formation from word⁴⁹¹. Furthermore, grammar is studied in syntax and it is an important aspect of a language. According to A.S. Hornby, grammar is defined as the rules in a language for changing the form of words and combining them into sentences⁴⁹². Every language has own grammatical rules and through contrastive studies of authentic syntactic patterns in context, new possibilities open up for additional insights, methodological renewals and empirical theory developments based on the study of sentence form. As S. Hunston and F. Sinclair put it: "There are gaps in the coverage of grammatical structures achieved by a generalisable system of structural analysis [...]"⁴⁹³.

Basically, grammar and translation skill are very important in learning another language. Some differences of grammatical systems between two languages can cause problems in translation process.

3. Dummy Subject

The concept of subject originally came from the study of Indo-European language family. Subject is obligatory in English with the exception of imperatives, and it plays syntactic and semantic roles, or just syntactic role as in the case of dummy subjects. In contrast, subject may be optional as in pro-drop languages such as Azeri, Persian and other. "It" as a dummy subject, it is semantically empty, has no referential function, no referent either in the discourse context or in the outside world. No thematic role can be assigned to it, and yet it keeps the most prominent thematic position of the sentence, i.e. the one of a subject. And to complicate things even further, no informative value or pragmatic prominence is directly encoded in the presence or absence of the dummy subject⁴⁹⁴.

D. Biber *et alii*⁴⁹⁵ identifies both semantically empty "it" and referentially empty "there" as formal grammatical subjects that appear in specific clause types. These are as follows:

- (1) *prop it*, denoting weather distance and time:

⁴⁹¹Yerkes, 1989, p. 1443.

⁴⁹²Hornby, 1995, p. 517.

⁴⁹³Hunston *et alii*, 2000, p. 75.

⁴⁹⁴Chocholoušova, 2007, p. 27.

⁴⁹⁵Biber *et alii*, 1999.

It starts raining.

(2) **existential clauses** (i.e. presentatives), introducing new information, and using verbs denoting existence, appearance and motion:

There are flagstones, garden gates, hedges, garages.

(3) **clefting-structural** clause division that brings focus to the clefted element:

It's mostly just rich folks who can afford a movin' company.

(4) **extraposition**–clauses where dummy subjects anticipate another finite or non-finite clause:

It takes a great effort to watch the moon for any length of time.

D. Biber *et alii* postulates that: «[...] the predicates here do not suggest any participant involved semantically, but [...] are obligatory inserted simply to complete the structure of the clause grammatically”.

Existential clauses, or presentative constructions, are the only constructions types that employ existential **there** as their formal, grammatical subject; the others use **it**. So is the case of “agentless processes” that are not listed in Biber *et alii*, nevertheless structurally possible in English:

It does not smell particularly great at Grandfather's.

The only exception here are “impersonal passives”⁴⁹⁶ that are structurally not allowed to be formed with intransitive verbs in English, hence, another types of subject must be inserted:

A commission of public inquiry was set up to study the incident, too.

4. Extraposition

Postponement which involves the replacement of the postponed element by a substitute form is termed **extraposition**. It operates almost exclusively on subordinate nominal clauses. The most important type of extraposition is that of a clausal subject-i.e. a subject realized by a finite or non-finite clauses⁴⁹⁷. According to Quirk *et alii*, the subject is moved to the end of the sentence and the normal subject position is filled by the anticipatory pronoun “it”. The resulting sentence thus contains two subjects, which may identify as the postponed subject, the one which is notionally the subject of the sentence and the anticipatory subject “it”. Simple rule for deriving a sentence with subject extraposition from one of more orthodox ordering is: **Subject + predicate ~ it + predicate + subject**. Thus: *To hear him say that + surprised me ~ It + surprised me + to hear him say that*.

⁴⁹⁶Quirk *et alii*, 1985, p. 1391.

⁴⁹⁷*ibidem*.

Some examples of this construction are shown as follows:

- (1) Type SVC: *It is a pleasure to teach her.*
- (2) Type SVA: *It was on the news that income tax is to be lowered.*
- (3) Type SV: *It does not matter what you do.*
- (4) Type SVO: *It seems that you have made a mistake.*
- (5) Type SVOC: *It makes him happy to see others enjoying themselves.*
- (6) Type SVpass: *It is said that she slipped arsenic his tea*⁴⁹⁸.

J. Herriman⁴⁹⁹ argues that the extraposition constructions are mainly used to express attitudinal meaning. In this research the Azeri translation of English extraposition constructions involving copular verbs and followed by *that*-clause and infinitive has been investigated.

5. Research Method

The purpose of this study is to investigate and analyze Azeri translation of English extraposition constructions involving copular verbs and followed by *that*-clause and infinitive. This research deals with analyzing of data in order to study Azeri translation of dummy subject *it*, *infinitive* and *that*-clause of English extraposition constructions.

5.1. Materials

The materials chosen for the analysis are English fictions which involve the novels of "For Whom the Bell Tolls" written by Hemingway, "400 Subjects in English" written by Vitalyevna, "Life Essays" written by Gurbanov, "The Alchemist" written by Coelho and Joyce's Dubliners (short stories).

200 extraposition constructions involving copular verbs and followed by infinitive and *that*-clause along with their translation into Azeri taken from Hajiyev (2006), Vitalyevna (2006), Gambarov (2010), Qojabayli (2006) and Nijat (2011) have been analyzed.

5.2. Procedures

The data are classified into two main categories: extraposition constructions followed by *infinitive* and extraposition constructions followed by *that*-clause.

5.3. Extraposition constructions followed by *infinitive*

The constructions which are translated as simple sentences without infinitive in Azeri:

- (1) *They seemed to be a happy couple at first.*
[əvvəlcə elə bil xoşbəxt cütlük idilər].
- (2) *It seemed to him to repeat itself throughout all the books.*

⁴⁹⁸*ibidem.*

⁴⁹⁹Herriman, 2004, p. 204.

[sanki bütün kitablarda elə hey eyni şey təkrarlanır].

(3) *It seems to me to remember things incorrectly.*

[məncə hər şeyi yaxşı saxlaya bilməmişəm].

(4) *It seemed to him to admire the horses.*

[sanki atlar tərifləməlidir].

(5) *It seems to me to know everything is useful for you.*

[elə bil hər şeyi bilmənin sənə faydalıdır].

(6) *It wonders me to see a gypsy a war.*

[məncə qaraçı müharibədə görməni nə nələsas şeydir].

(7) *It seems to agree with you.*

[görünür sənən şərik olmalıdır].

(8) *It seems to be sensitive and kind.*

[görünür həssas və yumşaq adamdır].

(9) *It sounds me to be interesting.*

[nə isə elə bil maraqlıdır].

(10) *It seemed to him to be little better guarded.*

[görünür düşərgənin müdafiəsi yaxşı təşkil olunmayıb].

The constructions which are translated as simple sentences involving infinitive in Azeri:

(1) *It pleases thee to carry it, he said.*

[əndə ki daşmaq istəyirsən, al... dedi].

(2) *It seems to the boy to flee.*

[ağlana qaçmaq gəlmişdi].

(3) *It seems to me to exterminate the post at the sawmill.*

[məncə taxta zavodundakı postu məhv etməkləzəmə].

(4) *It seems to him to go out.*

[görünür çıxmaq lazımdır].

(5) *It seems to keep down is the best.*

[görünür uzanmaq yaxşıdır].

5.4. Extraposition constructions followed by *that*-clause

The constructions which are translated as complex sentences in Azeri:

(1) *It seems to me that we might as well eat the hares.*

[mənə görünür ki dovşanlar isə bu gün yemək lazımdır].

(2) *It sounds me that it would be good to see Duran again.*

[yaxşı olardı ki Dürana bir də görüşşəydim].

(3) *It seems that you have an important intention.*

[görünür ki sənənin belə bir mühüm niyyətin var].

(4) *It seems that it is alright to stay here.*
[görünür ki burada qalmaq daha yaxşıdır].

(5) *It wonders me that the old swine will go.*
[maraqlıdır görəsən bu donuzolu hara gedir].

(6) *It wonders me that one pays as in the days of the church.*
[maraqlıdır ki biz kilsəyə pul verdiyimiz kimi, haqq versinlər].

(7) *It seems that the Republic is preparing an offensive.*
[görünür ki Respublika hücumu hazırlaşır].

(8) *It seems that I am barbarous.*
[görünür ki vəhşiyəm].

(9) *It wonders me that he might not understand.*
[maraqlıdır ki məni başa düşməz].

(10) *It seems that I can never bear either a son or a daughter.*
[görünür ki sənə oğlan və ya qız doğma bilməyəcəyəm].

The constructions which are translated as simple sentences in Azeri:

(1) *It seems to me that it is better not to speak of it.*
[məncə bu barədə danışmasaq yaxşıdır].

(2) *It seems that she is perfectly normal.*
[elə bil onda eybi yoxdur].

(3) *It sounds me that it is interesting.*
[elə bil maraqlı söhbətdir].

(4) *It seemed to him that they laugh at him.*
[elə bil Ehramlar ona gülümsədilər].

(5) *It seemed to him that he had made the long journey for nothing.*
[deməli boş yerə səyahətə çıxmışdır].

The constructions in which copular verbs have not translated in Azeri:

(1) *It sounds me that I am not good to receive thee as I wish to.*
Ø səninlə istədiyim kimi ola bilməyəcəyəm.

(2) *It seemed to him to see stars on the desert itself.*
Ø səhranın səmasında yüzlərcə ulduz parlaydı.

(3) *It seemed to him that time stood still.*
Ø kainatın Rohu cavan oğlanın önündü.

(4) *It seemed to him to be very busy.*
Ø işləri başlarından aşırması kimi görünürdülər.

(5) *It seemed to me that you have to cross the entire Sahara desert.*
Ø böyük saxara səhrasını keçmək lazımdır.

6. Data Findings

In this research, there are two main categories, namely, extraposition constructions followed by *that*-clause and the other one extraposition constructions followed by infinitive. Analyzing of 100 data related to the Azeri translation of English extraposition constructions followed by *that*-clause show that most of them are translated as complex sentences in Azeri with the percentage of 70%, and some translated as simple sentences with the percentage of 30% (*Table 1*). According to *Table 2* it has been cleared that 65% English extraposition constructions followed by infinitive, translated as simple sentences without infinitive and 35% translated as simple sentences involving infinitive in Azeri. *Table 3* shows that in Azeri dummy subject is not translated at all. Regarding the translation of copular verbs in Azeri, as shown in *Table 4*, they have either been replaced by some expressions called *Modal Words* or been omitted.

7. Discussion and Conclusion

Based on 200 data, it has been cleared that in Azeri ,dummy subject of English extraposition constructions is not translated. Regarding copular verbs, it should be mentioned that the copular verb “seem” is the most frequent one in this corpora, that is in 138 constructions this verb has been used. Results of analyzing of Azeri translation show that instead of copular verbs, there are some expressions in Azeri which are named *Modal Söz* like *Görünür, mənə, elə bil* [...] and according to the meaning of copular verbs, these expressions are used such as *görünür ki Respublika hücumu hazırlaşır*. Of course in some cases copular verbs are omitted as in:

(1) *It sounds me that I am not good to receive thee as I wish to.*

Ø səninlə istədiyim kimi ola *bilməyəcəyəm*.

Moreover, if there is an object after copular verbs, it is used before modal words, i.e in the beginning of the clause like “*mənə görünür ki dovşanlar isə bu gün yemək lazımdır*”.

According to the results of this research, English extraposition constructions followed by *that*-clause translated as complex sentences as in “*mənə görünür ki dovşanlar isə bu gün yemək lazımdır*”, and in some cases translated as simple sentences such as “*mənə bu barədə danışmasaq yaxşıdır*”.

Most of the English extraposition constructions followed by infinitive ,are translated as simple sentences without infinitive like *əvvəlcə elə bil xoşbəxt cütlük idilər*, however it should be mentioned in some constructions, infinitive translated as infinitive in Azeri, as in:

It seems to me to exterminate the post at the sawmill.

mənə taxta zavodundakı postu məhv etməklə lazımdır.

It can be concluded that English extraposition constructions which can be written as:

It + verb +(object)+that-clauses translated as *(object)+modal words +that clauses*

in Azeri:

It +verb+(object)+infinitive translated as *(object)+modal words +.....+verb.*

In this case it is necessary to mention that through contrastive studies of authentic syntactic patterns in context, new possibilities open up for additional insights, methodological renewals and empirical theory developments based on the study of sentences form. The main advantage of a bilingual or even multilingual parallel corpus is that the languages interrelate with each other. Moreover, it seems that in the literature of translation studies and in translation classrooms, students and learners are required to compare and contrast translations with their originals. It is useful for language learning, translation education, translation studies, lexicography, finding equivalents for SL expressions, terms, structures and so on. It is hoped that the results of the research may be used as additional information for the teachers especially in teaching English grammar and translation courses. Also, the results may help Azerbaijanian translators, English learners and translator trainees for being able to provide the best translation of English extraposition constructions.

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Tables

Table 1: The translation of the extraposition constructions followed by that-clause

	Total	Percentage
Complex sentences	70	70
Simple sentences	30	30

Table 2: The translation of the extraposition constructions followed by infinitive

	Total	Percentage
Simple sentences without infinitive	65	65
Simple sentences involving infinitive	35	35

Table 3: The translation of dummy subject

	Total

Dummy Subject	0
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Table 4: *The translation of copular verbs*

	Total
Using modal words	185
Deletion of copular verbs	15